

DIVERSITY AND ETHNOMEDICINAL PTERIDOPHYTES OF JALPAIGURI DISTRICT WEST BENGAL, INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The Jalpaiguri district of West Bengal lying the foothills of Eastern Himalaya at an elevation of 180-400 m may be considered as a resourceful area for pteridophytes. The present studies were carried out to collect, identify and documentation of ethnomedicinal properties of those pteridophytes. During the study period (2017-2020), seasonal field visits were carried out and a total of 45 ferns and fern-allies of different families were documented. The dominant families were Pteridaceae, Polypodiaceae and Thelypteridaceae. The study revealed different uses of ferns and fern-allies as food, fodder, treatment of various diseases, and as ornamental plants. This study may further help us for further exploitations of this group of plants and their conservation.

Key Words : Pteridophytes, Eastern Himalaya, Jalpaiguri.

INTRODUCTION

Pteridophytes are an important component of the flora in this major region of species-diversity, next to Angiosperms in number among the vascular plants. Human survival on planet Earth is dependent on a variety of plant species for medical and other useful characteristics. According to the World Health Organization, herbal medicines are used by over 80% of the population in most developing nations for their basic healthcare needs. In India, almost 80% of the population uses herbal medicine to treat a variety of ailments. Pteridophytes are known to humankind since the beginning of civilization as a source of green vegetables and medicinal plants. Since ancient times ferns have been used by mankind as food and medicine (Lee *et al.*, 2010). Charaka (3rd century BC) and Susruta (6th century BC) described uses of various pteridophytes in their Sanhitas. Theophrastus (327-287 BC) and Dioscorides (50 AD) had also referred to the medicinal attributes of certain ferns. They were identified to have various ethnomedicinal uses of ferns which could either be for food consumption or medicine and aesthetic value (Delos Angeles *et al.*, 2012). They also provide food, fiber, crafts, building material, abrasives and of course decoration materials (Srivastava, 2016, Sarkar *et al.*, 2017). The pteridophytic flora of Indian region is very rich due to remarkable altitudinal variations ranging from coastal level to high mountain ranges (Joshi *et al.*, 2018). In India about

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67 families, 191 genera and more than 1000 species of ferns and fern-allies are present (Dixit, 2000). Maximum number of diversity is found in the Eastern Himalayas, Kerala, Western and Eastern Ghats and Panchmarhi Biosphere Reserve (Bir, 1988; Sathiyaraj *et al.*, 2015).

India has a rich and varied pteridophytic flora due to its diversified topography, variable climatic conditions and its geographical position with several migration-flows of species of different Phyto-geographical elements meeting in different parts of the Country. Eastern Himalaya region has been recognized as one of the 34 global biodiversity hotspots with its unique floral features having one of the richest zone of fern vegetation about 500 taxa (480 species and 20 subspecies), grouped into 108 genera (Kholia, 2011).

Jalpaiguri district is one of the floristically rich and most varied district of West Bengal which is a part of the Eastern Himalaya foot-hills (Terai region) and northern most part of state West-Bengal with about 3386.18 sq. km area. Its geographical directs are between 26°15'47" to 26°59'34" N Latitude and 88°23'2" to 89°7'30" E Longitude. The altitude varies from 180 m in the foot-hill regions to more than 400 m small plateau with average annual rainfall approx. 250mm-300mm. The relative humidity varies 80-90% in monsoon season to 20% to 30% in spring-summer. The temperature of this area varies from 25°C to 36°C during summer and from 8°C to 22°C during

Figure : Different sampling sites of Jalpaiguri district

winter. The forests of Jalpaiguri district mainly extend from plains to Terai regions of Himalayas and are located in the flood plains of different main hill rivers and other medium and small rivers and rivulets which have created a pocket of grass land. Apart from Gorumara national park and wildlife sanctuaries a significant area of this district is covered by forest. The district is considered to be an important area for ecological and geographical purpose as it has a mixed microclimatic zone. The topography of the district varies from slightly hilly to foot hills, tropical evergreen and semi-evergreen forests, riverine regions to the transition of Terai and Dooars of Darjeeling hills. Thus it shows a wide variety of fern flora.

The vegetation is prominently Evergreen Forest, Savannahs, Riverine forest and swamps. The deciduous forests are predominately Sal (*Shorea robusta* Gaertn.); Savannahs are characterized by the presence of Amla (*Phyllanthusem blica* L.), Tarsing (*Beilschmiedia roxburghiana* Nees), Chilauri (*Schima wallichii* Choisy.), *Wrightia tinctoria* (Roxb.) R. Br, Jamun [*Syzygium cumini* (Linn.) Skeels], Sidha etc. and the deciduous Riverain forest having two dominant species Khair and Sissoo. Thus the fern flora shows much more diversity with the change in topography. The forest of Jalpaiguri bears its significance in the international context for providing shelter and protection to various species of wildlife included in the Red Data Book and appendices of CITES (Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora). District Jalpaiguri comprises of nine blocks: Jalpaiguri, Maynaguri, Dhupguri, Banarhat, Rajganj, Malbazar, Kranti, Matiali and Nagrakata. The district shares its borders with Bhutan at north, Bangladesh at southern part, Darjeeling district at western part and Alipurduar & Coochbehar at eastern most part. Many tribes residing in this district among them Rajbanshi, Rava, Toto, Mech, Santali, Lepcha, Bhutia and other Nepali tribes are the most prominent ethnic groups. Since ancient times, tribal tribes and ethnic groups have used various parts of fern and fern allies such as rhizome, fronds and pinnae in various methods to heal various diseases (Cherian and Ramteke, 2010). In some local communities, the traditional knowledge has become extinct or in the verge of extinction. Now-a-days the village folks depend more on the modern system of medication. In some communities, there was none to carry the knowledge to the next generations. Thus, it is important for proper documentation of the ethnic knowledge of considerable aspects in future generations (Sen and Ghosh, 2011). The ecosystem components in the region exhibit great dynamism and holds great significance from ecological and evolutionary point of view. Since medicinal pteridophytes and their derivatives continue to play an important role in medical treatment, it is critical to protect these resources for the sake of humanity and future generations.

GRAPH 1 : Family wise status of medicinal Fern and Fern-allies of Jalpaiguri district.

GRAPH 2 : Status of Habitat of Ferns.

GRAPH 3 : Status of medicinally used parts of Ferns.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research is based on a floristic survey, specimen collecting, and recurrent conversations with tribal peoples and herbal healers to acquire ethno-botanical knowledge. The fieldwork was undertaken different parts of the district from May 2017 to December 2020 comprising all the seasons with preparing herbarium sheets and deposited for ready

GRAPH 4 : Status of abundance of Fern species in different distribution sites.

reference in the herbarium of Pteridology and Palaeobotany laboratory, Department of Botany, University of North Bengal after critical study and identification of the plants were made as per available literature on various fern floras, research papers and through matching of the voucher specimens with the authentic records available on the Herbarium sheets of Kew and BSI (CAL) was done. The genera and species are classified according to PPG-I classification (PPG-I, 2016). Each specimen's habitat, ethnobotanical significance, and photographic documentation were all recorded during field visits. During this survey study, authors have collected 45 species of pteridophytes and out of these more than 40 species were used by natives as food, fodder, medicinal, ornamental and in ceremonial functions. Semi-structured questionnaire was adopted for data collection related to ethnobotany and compared with published literature representing different uses of pteridophytes throughout India.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ethnomedicinal uses of Fern species used by the different ethnic communities of Jalpaiguri district of West Bengal have been enumerated (Table 1). Total 45 species of fern and fern-allies belonging to 21 families under 31 genera were recorded from different parts of study areas among which 42 species are widely used by ethnic as well as common peoples (Table 1). Among these Pteridaceae family is the dominant one, represented by 12

TABLE 1 : Distribution, Abundance and Ethnobotanical importances of some Fern and Fern-allies of Jalpaiguri district.

Sl. No.	Botanical Name (Vernacular Name)	Habitat	Local Distribution	Abundance	Parts Used	Uses
Lycopodiaceae						
1.	<i>Lycopodium japonicum</i> Thunb.	Epiphytic	MAT, NAG	Rare	Whole plant	The plant paste is used for diuretic, antispasmodic, rheumatism and diseases of lungs and kidney.
2.	<i>Lycopodium cernuum</i> L.	Epiphytic	MAL, MAT, NAG, JPG, BAN, MAY, RAJ	Less	Whole plant	Whole plant decoction is used in beriberi, cough and the plant paste also applied externally over the cut portion to reduce swelling and itching.
SELAGINELLACEAE						
3.	<i>Selaginella monospora</i> Spring	Sciophyte, Lithophyte	MAL, MAT, NAG, KRA, BAN	Medium	Whole plant	Young plants are eaten as vegetable; dried plants are used as immortal substance by ethnic people.
4.	<i>Selaginella repanda</i> (Desv. & Poir.) Spring	Sciophyte, Lithophyte	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, KRA, BAN	High	Whole plant	Young plants are eaten as vegetable.
EQUISETACEAE						
5.	<i>Hippochaete debilis</i> (Roxb. ex Vaucher) Ching. [Horsetail] (<i>Equisetum debile</i>)	Terrestrial	MAT, KRA, RAJ, BAN, MAL, NAG, JPG	Medium	Whole plant	Decoction of plant is effective against diuretic, bleeding, gonorrhoea, joint pain, fungal infection and kidney disorders; plant paste is also applied in bone fracture.
OPHIOGLOSSACEAE						
6.	<i>Helminthostachys zeylanica</i> (L.) Hook.	Terrestrial, Sciophyte	NAG, MAL	Rare	Rhizome, Fronds	Rhizome is used to treat whooping cough, impotency and intoxicant; fronds used as aphrodisiac.
7.	<i>Ophioglossum petiolatum</i> Hook.	Terrestrial	JPG, MAY, DPG, MAL, MAT, BAN, RAJ, KRA	Medium	Leaves	Fresh fronds are eaten as green vegetable. The leaf paste is applied on burns as cooling agent and wound healing remedies.

Contd.

Contd. Table 1

GLEICHENIACEAE						
8.	<i>Dicranopteris linearis</i> (Burm. f.) Underw.	Terrestrial, Sciophyte	JPG, DPG, MAL, MAT, RAJ, NAG, MAY, KRA, BAN	Medium	Leaves	Young leaves paste mixed with cow milk are used to remove sterility in women; fronds used for thatching the roofs and house walls; extracts of fronds has shown laxative, antibacterial and antioxidant activity and used for treating cuts, boil, ulcers, asthma, fever.
LYGODIACEAE						
9.	<i>Lygodium flexuosum</i> (L.) Sw. [Bhutraj]	Terrestrial, Sciophyte	JPG, DPG, MAL, MAT, RAJ, NAG, MAY, BAN, KRA	Medium	Rhizome, Leaves	The decoction of rhizome is used against gonorrhoea, jaundice, piles; rhizome boiled with mustard oil is applied to carbuncles and in rheumatism, sprains, scabies, ulcers, eczema and cuts. The leaves are used to prepare rice-beer.
SALVINIACEAE						
10.	<i>Salvinia cucullata</i> Roxb.	Aquatic	RAJ, JPG, KRA, MAL	Medium	Whole plant	Whole plant is used as poultry and cattle feed; use to increase the fertility of rice field; it is often used as antibacterial and insecticides.
11.	<i>Salvinia natans</i> (L.) All.	Aquatic	JPG, DPG, MAL, MAT, RAJ, NAG, MAY, BAN, KRA	High	Whole plant	Whole plant is used as duck feed.
12.	<i>Azolla pinnata</i> R. Br.	Aquatic	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, BAN, KRA	High	Whole plant	Whole plant is used as food supplement or fodder in fresh or dried or silage form for variety of domestic animals.
MARSILEACEAE						
13.	<i>Marsilea minuta</i> L. [Sushni Sak]	Aquatic	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, BAN, KRA	High	Leaves	Young fronds are eaten as vegetable; also used to treat against cough, spastic conditions of leg muscles, insomnia and mental problems.

Contd.

Contd. Table 1

CYATHEACEAE						
14.	<i>Cyathea gigantea</i> (Wall. ex Hook.) Holttum. [Tree Fern]	Terrestrial	MAL, MAT, KRA	Less	Rhizome, Petiole	Decoction of rhizome and young petiole is given in snake bite; Paste of fresh rhizome is used locally on the cuts and boils. It has antitumor, antiviral and hepato-protective activity.
LINDSAEACEAE						
15.	<i>Odontosoria chinensis</i> (L.) J. Sm.	Marshy Sciophyte	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, BAN, KRA	Medium	Whole plant	Paste of the plant used in swelling and sprains. Dried fronds are used as a substitute for tea leaves used internally for chronic enteritis and used as diuretic.
PTERIDACEAE						
16.	<i>Antrophyum coriaceum</i> (D. Don) Wall. ex T. Moore	Epiphytic	MAL, MAT, NAG	Less	Whole plant	Use as ornamental purposes.
17.	<i>Pteris vittata</i> subsp. <i>vittata</i> L.	Lithophyte	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, BAN, KRA	High	Leaves, Rhizome	Paste of leaves and rhizome are used to treat cut and wounds. Frond decoction is taken as tonic for cough remedy.
18.	<i>Pteris semipinnata</i> L.	Terrestrial, Sciophyte	JPG, RAJ, MAL, MAT, NAG, DPG, MAY, BAN, KRA	Medium	FronDS	Paste of FronDS is applied locally around carbuncle for cure and also to reduce pain.
19.	<i>Pteris biaurita</i> subsp. <i>fornicate</i> Fraser-Jenk.	Terrestrial, Sciophyte	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, BAN, KRA	High	Rhizome and fronds	A decoction of the rhizome and fronds has been given in chronic disorders.
20.	<i>Ceratopteris thaliktroides</i> (L.) Brongn. [Jol Agacha]	Aquatic	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, BAN, KRA	High	FronDS	Young fronds are eaten as vegetable; Decoction of fronds is used against Skin diseases, wounds, stomach-ache and piles.
21.	<i>Adiantum philipines</i> L.	Lithophyte, Epiphytic	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, BAN, KRA	Medium	Leaves, Root	The leaf and root decoction are used for treatment of cough, asthma, fever, leprosy and hair falling; it is also useful in the treatment of throat swellings in the cattle.

Contd.

Contd. Table 1

22.	<i>Adiantum capillus-veneris</i> L.	Lithophyte	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, BAN, KRA	High	Fronds	The fronds are used as a garnish on sweet dishes. The dried fronds are used to make a tea; the juice of fresh plants for curing cough and diabetes; the plants under the bed for the prevention of chicken pox.
23.	<i>Adiantum caudatum</i> L. [GoyaliLata]	Lithophyte, Epiphytic	JPG, RAJ, MAY, DPG, BAN	Medium	Fronds, Rhizome	Decoction of fronds and rhizome are used in fever and cough.
24.	<i>Adiantum incisum</i> Forssk.	Lithophyte	JPG, RAJ, DPG, MAY, MAT, MAL	Less	Leaves	The leaf powder is mixed with butter and used for controlling the internal burning of the body. Also used in cough, diabetes, fever and skin diseases.
25.	<i>Vittaria elongata</i> Swartz	Epiphytic	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, BAN, KRA	Medium	Leaves	The leaf paste is applied extremely to get relief from knee pain, therapeutic pain, cuts, wounds, rheumatism & joint pains.
26.	<i>Pityrogramma calomelanos</i> (L.) Link [Silver Fern]	Terrestrial	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, BAN, KRA	High	Whole plant	Decoction of leaves are used to heal wounds and stop bleeding; also used against kidney trouble, body insects, fever, hypertension, cough, measles, boils in mouth & nose, wounds, gastric disorders, fever, cold, asthma, anti helminthic, cancer.
27.	<i>Onychium siliculosum</i> (Desv.) C. Chr. [Golden Fern]	Terrestrial, Sciophyte	MAL, MAT, NAG, BAN, KRA, JPG, RAJ	Less	Fronds	Decoction of fronds used against dysentery, hair fall and skin diseases.
DENNSTAEDTIACEAE						
28.	<i>Microlepia speluncae</i> (L.) T. Moore	Terrestrial	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, BAN, KRA	High	Whole plant	Decoction of plant is useful against various eye diseases.
ASPENIACEAE						
29.	<i>Asplenium finlaysonianum</i> Wall. ex Hook.	Lithophyte, Sciophyte	MAL	Rare	Root	Decoction of root is used for Dysentery.

Contd.

Contd. Table 1

30.	<i>Asplenium nidus</i> L.	Epiphytic	MAL, MAT, JPG, NAG, RAJ, BAN	Less	Leaves	They also used in Home decoration, contraceptive, depurative and sedative; decoction of leaves is also used for treatment of chest pains, calculus, jaundice, malaria, cough-cold and stings & bite. Home decoration.
31.	<i>Asplenium crinicaule</i> Hance	Epiphytic	MAT, MAL, NAG	Less		Not yet known.
BLECHNACEAE						
32.	<i>Blechnum orientale</i> L.	Terrestrial	MAL, JPG, RAJ, MAT, NAG, DPG, MAY, BAN, KRA	Medium	Pinnae	Hot decoction of pinnae is applied for cut and wounds as antiseptic.
ATHYRIACEAE						
33.	<i>Diplazium esculentum</i> (Ritz.) Sw. [Dheki Sak]	Sciophyte	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, BAN, KRA	High	Fronde	Young fronds are eaten as vegetable; the plant is used in treating headache, pain and fever.
THELYPTERIDACEAE						
34.	<i>Thelypteris dentata</i> (Forssk.) E.P. St. John [Bisdhenkia]	Terrestrial	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, BAN, KRA	High	Fronde	Decoction of young fronds is useful against swellings, rheumatism, blood vomiting, urinary disorders, insect repellent, wounds & cuts.
35.	<i>Thelypteris triphylla</i> (Swartz) K. Iwatsuki	Marshy Sciophyte	RAJ, MAT, MAL	Less	Fronde	Mature fronds are served as home decoration purposes.
36.	<i>Thelypteris nudata</i> (Roxburgh) Morton	Terrestrial, Sciophyte	MAL, MAT, NAG, KRA, BAN, RAJ, DPG, MAY, JPG	Medium	Whole plant	Decoction of pinnae is used for treatment of acute pyorrhoea.
37.	<i>Thelypteris arida</i> (Don) Morton	Terrestrial, Sciophyte	MAL, MAT, NAG, KRA, BAN, RAJ, DPG, MAY, JPG	High	Whole plant	Plant paste is applied in wounds and cuts.
DRYOPTERIDACEAE						
38.	<i>Polystichum lentum</i> (D. Don) T. Moore	Terrestrial, Sciophyte	MAT	Less		Not yet known.

Contd.

Contd. Table 1

NEPHROLEPIDACEAE						
39.	<i>Nephrolepis cordifolia</i> (L.) C. Presl	Terrestrial, Sciophyte	MAL, MAT, NAG, BAN	Less	Root tubers, Leaves	The Fresh watery root tubers are eaten to especially quench thirst and edible as cooked vegetable; paste of the leaves is applied to cut and wounds. Decoction of tubers is given to cure cough and intestinal disorders.
TECTARIACEAE						
40.	<i>Tectaria coadunata</i> C. Chr.	Marshy Sciophyte	MAL, MAT, NAG, RAJ, DPG, BAN	Medium	Leaves, Rhizome	Decoction of leaves is useful against colitis; decoction of rhizome is given to children in stomach-ache.
DAVALLIACEAE						
41.	<i>Davallia trichomanoides</i> Blume	Epiphytic	MAT, MAL	Less	Rhizome	Rhizome is used against typhoid and anthelmintic.
POLYPODIACEAE						
42.	<i>Drynaria quercifolia</i> (L.) J. Sm. [Pankhiraj]	Epiphytic, Lithophyte	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, BAN, KRA	High	Pinnae, Rhizome, Fronds	Pinnae paste is applied externally on fractured bones for setting up the bones. Sometimes rhizome and fronds paste is applied externally for blood clotting, tuberculosis and throat infections.
43.	<i>Microsorium punctatum</i> (L.) Copel. [Fish tail]	Epiphytic, Lithophyte	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, BAN, KRA	High	Fronds	Fronds use as chicken and cattle feed; Use to increase the fertility of rice field. It has antibacterial and insecticides. It is also useful against constipation, urinary disorders, snakebite, dysentery and for healing wounds.
44.	<i>Pyrrhosia lanceolata</i> (L.) Farw.	Epiphytic, Lithophyte	JPG, MAL, MAT, NAG, MAY, DPG, RAJ, BAN, KRA	High	Leaves	Decoction of leaves is used for curing cold and sore throats.
45.	<i>Pyrrhosia costata</i> Tagawa & K. Iwats.	Epiphytic	MAL, MAT, NAG, BAN	Less		Not yet known.

Abbreviations : JPG - Jalpaiguri, RAJ - Rajganj, MAY - Maynaguri, DPG - Dhupguri, BAN - Banarhat, MAL - Malbazaar, MAT - Matiali, KRA - Kranti, NAG - Nagrakata

PLATE-I : 1. *Lycopodium japonicum* Thunb.; 2. *Blechnum orientale* L.; 3. *Onychium siliculosum* (Desv.) C. Chr.; 4. *Lycopodium cernuum* L.; 5. *Thelypteris dentata* (Forssk.) E.P. St. John; 6. *Microlepia speluncae* (L.) T. Moore; 7. *Pteris biaurita* subsp. *fornicate* Fraser-Jenk.; 8. *Thelypteris nudata* (Roxburgh) Morton; 9. *Pyrrosia lanceolata* (L.) Farw.; 10. *Asplenium crinicaule* Hance; 11. *Adiantum philippense* L.; 12. *Microsorium punctatum* (L.) Copel.

PLATE-II : 13. *Adiantum incisum* Forssk.; 14. *Selaginella repando* (Desv. & Poir.) Spring; 15. *Lygodium flexuosum* (L.) Sw.; 16. *Cyathea gigantia* (Wall. ex Hook.) Holttum.; 17. *Marsilea minuta* L.; 18. *Thelypteris arida* (Don) Morton; 19. *Diplazium esculentum* (Retz.) Sw.; 20. *Drynaria quercifolia* (L.) J. Sm.; 21. *Vittaria elongate* Swartz.; 22. *Salvinia cucullata* Roxb.; 23. *Salvinia natans* (L.) All.; 24. *Azolla pinnata* R. Br.

sp. followed by Thelypteridaceae and Polypodiaceae families represented by 6 spp. People in the area utilize pteridophytes for a variety of purposes, including medicinal, food, fodder, and other multifunctional applications. Fern fronds are also used to decorate homes for a variety of events. In the present study, the different ethnic communities of this area are found to use some common pteridophytes in their routine health care system to treat the diseases like cold, fever, gonorrhoea, dental problems, cardiac problem, burning wounds, skin diseases, mental disorders, stomach ulcer and acidity, jaundice, abdominal and respiratory disorders and home decoration. *Blechnum orientale* L., *Ophioglossum petiolatum* Hook., *Marsilea minuta* L., *Ceratopteris thalictroides* (L.) Brongn., *Diplazium esculentum* (Retz.) Sw., *Selaginella repando* (Desv. & Poir.) Spring, *Selaginella monospora* Spring are widely used as green vegetables and sold in local markets. Some of the pteridophytes are used as ethnoveterinary (fodder of poultry) like *Salvinia cucullata* Roxb., *Salvinia natans* (L.) All. and *Azolla pinnata* R. Br. Recently *Azolla pinnata* R. Br. enormously uses by farmer as biofertilizer in the rice fields. Many of them are found to use by ethnic people as ornamental purposes like *Antrophyum coriaceum* (D. Don) Wall. ex T. Moore, *Thelypteris triphylla* (Swartz) K. Iwatsuki, *Asplenium nidus* L.

CONCLUSION

Pteridophytes are moisture and shade-loving plants that rely on the microclimatic conditions of their environment to thrive. Any disruption to these microclimatic conditions might stymie the natural development and evolutionary processes that occur in these plants, resulting in population decrease. As a result, issues such as climate change and land encroachment for various constructions represent a significant danger to the survival of many fern groups. The purpose of this study is to investigate and comprehend the variety, ecology, and usage of pteridophytic flora of the said biodiversity rich district. The present study is useful for ethno-botanist, phyto-chemists and pharmacologists working on medicinal ferns and fern-allies. Also, economic aspect of this paper may increase the rural economy. Also, medicinal uses of these plants may be utilized as an alternative source of drugs for the benefit of mankind in a manner without affecting the natural ecosystem. Conservation and cultivation of these ferns and fern-allies will help to maintain the ecological balance, traditional knowledge as well as livelihood security of local inhabitants. This might assist toraise public awareness about the need for conservation of ferns and promote ethno-medico-botany knowledge in the region, as well as contribute to the preservation and enrichment of the natural riches of such a biodiversity-rich district before they are lost forever. Hope this study will be helpful for natives and ethno botanists for further critical investigation of medicinal and other economical uses of plants present in this area.

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REFERENCES

- BIR, S. S. 1988. Evolutionary trends in the Pteridophytic flora of India. Presidential address, Section of Botany, Indian Science Congress Platinum Jubilee Session 1977, *Proc. Indian Sci. Congr.* 75: 1-56, Calcutta.
- CHERIAN, K.J. & RAMTEKE, D.D. 2010. Ethnomedicinal Ferns Species used by Tribals of Gondia District, Vidarbha Region of Maharashtra. *International Journal for Environmental Rehabilitation and Conservation.* 1(1): 73-77.
- DELOS ANGELES, M. & BUOT, I. 2012. Orders and Families of Philippine Pteridophytes. *Journal of Nature Studies.* 11(1&2): 19-33
- DIXIT, R.D. 2000. Conspectus of pteridophytic Diversity in India. *Indian Fern J.* 17: 77-91
- FAO.WHO Fact Sheet No. 2002, 271.
- JOSHI, B., TEWARI, S., SHUKLA, B.K. & SRIVASTAVA, A. 2018. Diversity of Fern and Fern-Allies of Tarai West Forest Division, Ramnagar, Uttarakhand. *Indian Forester* 144(12): 1194-1197 (2018).
- KHOLIA, B.S. 2011. Pteridophytic wealth of Sikkim Himalaya. In: *Biodiversity of Sikkim* (Arrawatia, M.L. and Tambe, S., Ed.), Govt. of Sikkim 35-68.
- LEE, C.H. & SHIN, S.L. 2010. Functional activities of ferns for human health. In H. Fernández, M.A. Revilla, and A. Kumar (eds.), *Working with ferns: Issues and applications.* Springer, New York, pp. 347-359.
- PPG-I. 2016. A community-derived classification for extant lycophytes and ferns. *J. Syst. Evol.* 54(6) : 563-603.
- SARKAR, A.K., DEY, M. & MAZUMDER, M. 2017. Ecological status of medicinal plants of Chalsa forest range under Jalpaiguri division, West Bengal, India. *International Journal of Herbal Medicine.* 5(5): 196-215.
- SATHIYARAJ, G., MUTHUKUMAR, T. & RAVINDRAN, K.C. 2015. Ethnomedicinal Importance of fern and fern allies traditionally used by tribal people of Palani Hills. *J. Medicinal Herbs and Ethnomedicine.* 1(1): 4-9.
- SEN A. & GHOSH P.D. 2011. A note on the ethnobotanical studies of some pteridophytes in Assam. *Ind. J. of Traditional Knowledge.* 10(2): 292-295.
- SRIVASTAVA, K. 2016. Importance of Ferns in Human Medicine. *Ethnobotanical Leaflets* 11: 231-234 (2016).